

Izaskun Dávila, Oihana Gordobil, Jalel Labidi, Patricia Gullón, Assessment of suitability of vine shoots for hemicellulosic oligosaccharides production through aqueous processing, *Bioresource Technology*, Volume 211, 2016, Pages 636-644. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.03.153>
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0960852416304564>)

Abstract: Vine shoots were subjected to non-isothermal aqueous processing. A range of severities (S_0) from 3.20 to 4.65 was assayed and their effects in terms of solubilization, composition, molar mass distribution, structural characterization and thermal stability of the liquors were studied using HPLC, HPSEC, TGA and FTIR. The spent solids were characterized by HPLC and FTIR. When autohydrolysis was carried out at $S_0 = 4.01$, the substrate solubilization achieved a 38.7% of the raw material and 83.1% of the initial xylan was converted into xylooligosaccharides (XOS). The amount of TOS (total oligosaccharides) in the hydrolysates was 28.4 g/L while the other non volatile compounds (ONVC) were 0.08 g/g NVC. The spent solid from the treatment at $S_0 = 4.01$ was composed about 90% of cellulose and lignin. Therefore, it can be concluded that autohydrolysis is a suitable pretreatment of vine shoots such as a first stage of a biomass refinery.

Keywords: Vine shoots, Autohydrolysis, Hemicelluloses, Oligosaccharides, Biorefinery

Assessment of suitability of vine shoots for hemicellulosic oligosaccharides production through aqueous processing

Izaskun Dávila, Oihana Gordobil, Jalel Labidi, Patricia Gullón*

Chemical and Environmental Engineering Department, University of the Basque Country, 20018 San Sebastián, Spain

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: patricia.gullon@ehu.es (P. Gullón).

Abstract:

Vine shoots were subjected to non-isothermal aqueous processing. A range of severities (S_0) from 3.20 to 4.65 was assayed and their effects in terms of solubilization, composition, molar mass distribution, structural characterization and thermal stability of the liquors were studied using HPLC, HPSEC, TGA and FTIR. The spent solids were characterized by HPLC and FTIR. When autohydrolysis was carried out at $S_0 = 4.01$, the substrate solubilization achieved a 38.7% of the raw material and 83.1% of the initial xylan was converted into xylooligosaccharides (XOS). The amount of TOS (total oligosaccharides) in the hydrolysates was 28.4 g/L while the other non volatile compounds (ONVC) were 0.08 g/g NVC. The spent solid from the treatment at $S_0 = 4.01$ was composed about 90% of cellulose and lignin. Therefore, it can be concluded that autohydrolysis is a suitable pretreatment of vine shoots such as a first stage of a biomass refinery.

Keywords: Vine shoots, autohydrolysis, hemicelluloses, oligosaccharides, biorefinery

1. Introduction

In the last two decades, there has been a growing interest in lignocellulosic biomass, as it is one of the most promising sustainable resources to substitute fossil based fuels, chemicals and materials (Deutschmann and Dekker, 2012). In this sense, the agricultural activities generate a high volume of residues of lignocellulosic nature. Between these activities, grape crops are one of the main extended agro economic activities in the world with more than 60 million tons of it produced globally every year (Teixeira et al., 2014). The wine making industry generates huge amounts of wastes; in fact for each kilogram of grape which is pressed into wine, more than 20% is residue (Marculescu and Ciuta, 2013), which corresponds to grape marc, bagasse and lees. Another important grape waste generated in high quantities are the vine shoots, for each hectare of cultivation from 2 to 4 tons of these residues are produced from the pruning of the vine (Nabais et al., 2010). The conventional way to get rid of the vine shoots is by leaving them on the ground to rot or by using them as a source of energy by their combustion (Sánchez-Gómez et al., 2014). The vine shoots is mainly composed by three fractions: cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin (Delgado-Torre et al., 2012), making them suitable raw materials to be transformed into precursors for the chemical, food, and pharmaceutical industries by fractionation processes.

In this sense, several researches have been carried out to use vine shoots for materials applications and as a source of high-added value compounds. The main application for this material has been focused on the preparation of cellulose pulp (Jiménez et al., 2004). The vine shoots have been also studied as a source of polyphenols (Max et al., 2010) and as a source of renewable sugars that were converted into products such lactic acid, xylitol (Rivas et al., 2007) or ethanol (Jiménez et al., 2007).

Fractionation of lignocellulosic is the core of the “biomass refinery” concept, the aim of which is to break up the main polymers that integrate biomass (i.e., cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin) and further process them into marketable final products. On the other hand, nowadays there is a trend that encourages the use of free environmental techniques to enhance sustainability, it is the so-called “green chemistry” (Sánchez-Gómez et al., 2014). In this sense, the hydrothermal process (autohydrolysis) of lignocellulosic materials (in which water and feedstock are the only reagents) is an environmentally friendly process for biomass utilization; this treatment enables a high solubilization of hemicellulosic fraction in the reaction liquors and provides a solid phase enriched into cellulose and lignin with high recovery (Moniz et al., 2013).

Hemicelluloses are substituted xylans, where the main backbone of the 1–4-linked β -D-xylopyranose units can be substituted with arabinose, galactose, mannose, rhamnose, uronic acid moieties (or their 4-O-methyl ethers), ferulic acid and acetyl groups (Vegas et al., 2005), inter alia. Although the hemicelluloses have been much less valued and less exploited than the other fractions from biomass, in the recent years, the interest on oligosaccharides derived from

hemicelluloses has increased because they could be used in a variety of rising applications such as in healthcare, cosmetics, biopolymers, coatings, and other industries (Chemin et al., 2015).

In the literature the different pretreatments carried out using the vine shoots in order to increase the cellulose susceptibility and to recover the hemicellulosic sugars have been the acid hydrolysis (Rivas et al., 2007), or the autohydrolysis followed by an acid hydrolysis (Moldes et al., 2007). Between the two different pretreatments employed with the vine shoots, the autohydrolysis presents some advantages compared with the acid hydrolysis: water is used without the addition of any chemicals, there is no need of a chemical recovery unit or a treatment of effluents, as no acid is used the corrosion will be less (Carvalho et al., 2004). In the literature, there are many examples of the obtention of oligosaccharides by autohydrolysis from different agricultural feedstocks, such a sugar beet pulp (Martínez et al., 2010a), *Pinus pinaster* (Rivas et al., 2012) or rye straw (Gullón et al., 2010) among others.

In this work, we propose the use of an aqueous pretreatment as a first stage of an integrated biorefinery of vine shoots. Therefore, the goal was to assess the suitability of the vine shoots to obtain hemicellulosic oligosaccharides through their selective fractionation in aqueous media in addition to obtain a solid fraction for further friendly environmental processing. This biorefinery approach allows the separation of the three major fractions of vine shoots and their further use for several applications. The effects of the pretreatment on the liquid and solid phases were evaluated and interpreted in basis to the severity factor S_0 ($\log R_0$) in order to determine the best conditions to achieve the maximum solubilisation of hemicelluloses with the minimum generation of monosaccharides and non-saccharide compounds. Likewise, the effects on cellulose and lignin were also assayed. The characterization of the solubilized hemicelluloses from autohydrolysis was carried out using different analytical techniques (HPLC, HPSEC, TGA and FTIR). The spent solids were characterized by HPLC and FTIR.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Raw material

The vine shoots from the variety Hondarribi Zuri were supplied by the local winery Aldako Bodega S.L. in Oiartzun (Basque Country, Spain). The vine shoots once collected were milled and sieved to obtain a fraction with a particle size lower than 0.4 mm. The milled vine shoots were air-dried up to constant moisture, homogenized in a single lot to avoid compositional variations among aliquots and finally stored in a dry dark place until use.

2.2. Analysis of the raw material

Aliquots from the homogenized vine shoots were subject to moisture (TAPPI T264-om-88), ashes (TAPPI T244-om-93) and ethanol-toluene extractives (TAPPI T204cm-97) determination. To

determine the content of hemicelluloses, cellulose and lignin, the raw material was milled and sieved to obtain a particle size lower than 0.25 mm. This determination was carried by a conventional quantitative acid hydrolysis with 72% H₂SO₄ (TAPPI T-249-em-85). The liquid phase was analyzed by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) with a Jasco LC Net II/ADC chromatograph equipped with a refractive index detector and a photodiode array detector. A sample of the liquid phase was used for the analysis of acetic acid, galacturonic acid and the degradation products (furfural (F) and hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF)) using a Phenomenex Rezex ROA column; the mobile phase (0.005 N H₂SO₄) was eluted at a flow rate of 0.35 mL/min at 60 °C. Another sample of the liquid phase after its neutralization with BaCO₃ was used for the determination of monosaccharides (glucose, xylose, arabinose, galactose, mannose) using a Transgenomic CARBOsep CHO-682 column; the mobile phase was H₂O at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min at 80 °C. The oven-dried weight of the solid phase obtained from quantitative acid hydrolysis was considered as Klason lignin. All analyses were made by triplicate.

2.3. Hydrothermal processing of vine shoots

Vine shoots (with a particle size lower than 0.4 mm) and water were mixed at the desired proportions and reacted in a 1.5 L stainless steel 5100 Parr reactor under non-isothermal conditions at a liquid-to-solid ratio of 8 kg/kg (oven-dried basis) following the standard heating temperature profile and heated in the range of temperature 180–215 °C, controlled through a Parr PID control. The temperature profile followed during the heating and cooling process of the reactor is shown in Fig. 1. In order to facilitate the comparisons between different reactors and to measure the intensity of the hydrothermal pretreatments, the combined effects caused by the time and temperature during the non-isothermal treatments, including heating and cooling periods, were measured in terms of the Severity (S_0), defined as (Vargas et al., 2015):

$$S_0 = \log R_0 = \log[R_{0Heating} + R_{0Cooling}]$$

$$= \log \left[\int_0^{t_{Max}} e^{\left(\frac{T(t)-T_{Ref}}{\omega}\right)} dt + \int_{t_{Max}}^{t_F} e^{\left(\frac{T'(t)-T_{Ref}}{\omega}\right)} dt \right]$$

where R_0 is the severity factor, t_{Max} is the time (in min) needed to achieve the maximum temperature of each autohydrolysis treatment (T_{Max} , °C); t_F is the time (in min) required for the entire heating–cooling cycles; $T(t)$ and $T'(t)$ (°C) are the temperature profiles in heating and cooling, respectively, and ω and T_{Ref} are parameters whose values have been reported in the literature ($\omega = 14.75$ °C; $T_{Ref} = 100$ °C).

Fig. 1. Temperature profile of the hydrothermal processing

2.3.1. Analysis of solid fractions

Spent solids from the hydrothermal treatments were recovered by filtration, washed with water, air-dried and subjected to gravimetric and moisture determination to measure the solid yield and the amount of solubilized substrate. The spent solids were subjected to the same analytical processing as the raw material.

2.3.2.. Chemical characterization of hydrolysates

Samples of liquors from each treatment were analyzed by HPLC as described in Section 2.2. Another sample from each treatment was subjected to quantitative posthydrolysis (treatment with 4% H₂SO₄ at 121 °C for 30 min) and the monosaccharides and acetic acid present in liquors posthydrolyzed were assayed by HPLC. The increase in the concentrations of monosaccharides and acetic acid caused by posthydrolysis provided a measure of the oligomer concentration and their degree of substitution by acetyl groups. Before analysis on a CARBOSep CHO 682 column for monosaccharides quantification, posthydrolyzed samples were neutralized with BaCO₃ as described in Section 2.2. For analyses of the acids and degradation products on a Phenomenex Rezex ROA column, the posthydrolyzed samples were injected directly. OS were expressed as monosaccharide equivalents.

The content of non-volatile compounds (NVC) in liquid phases was determined by oven-drying at 105 ± 5 °C until constant weight. The quantification of non-saccharides, non-volatile compounds (denoted as other non-volatile compounds, ONV) was carried out by difference between the NVC and saccharides (including monosaccharides, OS and OS substituents) in liquors (Gullón et al., 2010).

2.3.3. Structural characterization of hydrolysates

2.3.3.1. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR analysis was performed on a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer. A total of 8 scans were accumulated in transmission mode with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The spectrum was obtained from a range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Previously to the FTIR analyses the liquid phases from the pretreatments carried out at the assayed temperatures were frozen at -18 °C and then freeze-dried.

2.3.3.2. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out with TGA/SDTA RSI analyzer 851 Mettler Toledo. The freeze-dried liquors from the autohydrolysis experiments were analyzed to determinate their thermal stability. Samples of about 3–5 mg were tested under nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 25 °C to 600 °C. Previously to the TGA analyses the liquid phases from the pretreatments carried out at the assayed temperatures were frozen at -18 °C and then freeze-dried.

2.3.3.3. Molecular weight distribution (high performance size exclusion chromatography (HPSEC)).

The molar mass distribution of the oligosaccharides present in the autohydrolysis liquors was analysed by HPSEC with a Jasco LC Net II/ADC chromatograph equipped with a refractive index detector and a photodiode array detector using a Varian Polymer Laboratories aquagel-OH mixed-H 8µm column. The conditions used for eluting the sample (40 µL) were a temperature of 40 °C; 0.005 N H₂SO₄ as the mobile phase; a flow of 0.6 mL/min. The calibration of the HPSEC was carried using pullulan polysaccharides with different molecular weights (between 180 and 805,000 Da).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Chemical characterization of the raw material

The results of the compositional data of the vine shoots used on this work (expressed as g/100 g oven dry basis) were in agreement with the ones obtained by Moldes et al. (2007).

The glucan content resulted in a 33.2% of the dry weight of the raw material. Similar percentages were reported by Gullón et al. (2009) for mixed herbs (31.6%), mainly belonging to the *Lylium* species.

Hemicelluloses (measured as the joint contribution of xylan, arabinosyl substituents, galactosyl substituents, manosyl substituents, acetyl groups and galacturonic acid) accounted for 27% of the dry weight of the raw material (measured as the joint contribution of xylan (12.3%), arabinosyl

substituents (1.4%), galactosyl substituents (3.2%), manosyl substituents (1.6%), acetyl groups (4.3%) and galacturonic acid (4.1%). This content was analogous to some agroindustrial subproducts such as rye straw (30.2%) (Gullón et al., 2010) or sunflowers seed hulls (28.6%) (Gullón et al., 2009). The composition of the hemicelluloses, in molar ratio, calculated from the compositional data, is xylose:arabinose:acetyl groups = 10:1.17:10.7, confirming a high degree of acetylation of this fraction; these ratio is in agreement with the results reported by other authors for some hemicellulosic heteropolysaccharides (Bustos et al., 2004).

The lignin percentage (26.7%) was similar to the one reported for some agricultural residues such as sunflowers seed hulls (29.4%) (Gullón et al., 2009).

Other fractions present in fewer amounts, such as ashes and extractives (2.6% and 3.1%, respectively), were determined to characterize the raw material in depth.

3.2. Non isothermal aqueous processing of vine shoots

In basis to the chemical composition of vine shoots, we considered that this feedstock is a suitable candidate to obtain hemicellulosic derived oligosaccharides. With the aim to explore this possibility we carried out a set of aqueous processing to determine the optimum conditions to solubilize the maximum of hemicelluloses. In the next section, the results obtained in this work are discussed.

3.2.1. Effects of the severity of hydrothermal treatments on vine shoot solubilization and on the hydrolysate composition

To assess the suitability of vine shoots on the production of oligosaccharides using aqueous treatments, several temperatures were tested in the range 180–215 °C under non-isothermal conditions. Table 1 lists the severities (S_0), the percentage of the raw material solubilization and the chemical composition of the spent solids from aqueous processing in the range of temperatures evaluated. The percentage of the substrate solubilization increased continuously with severity; the results show that the solubilisation percentage experimented a sharp increase in the range 180–200 °C (from 24.2% to 38.7% of dry raw material); however, additional severity increases resulted on an almost constant solubilisation percentage (scarcely an increase of 1.4% from 200 to 215 °C) being the weight loss rate slower in this range. The maximum percentage of solubilization was 40.5% of the initial mass on dry basis under the severest conditions assayed (215 °C that corresponds with a severity of 4.65). Similar results of substrate solubilization percentage have been informed by other authors working with other lignocellulosic materials such as rye straw (Gullón et al., 2010) or with wood as *Acacia dealbata* (Yáñez et al., 2009) with solubilisation percentages of 43% and 42% of the raw material respectively, at the highest temperature studied. The weight loss of raw material during the treatments is consequence of the selective

solubilisation of the hemicellulosic fraction and other minor soluble fractions (without interest in this work and therefore not identified) on liquid phase yielding a spent solid phase enriched in glucan and Klason lignin (both fractions less susceptible to hydrothermal processing).

Table 1. Severity of hydrothermal treatments, substrate solubilization (expressed as percentage of dry raw material) and chemical composition of spent solids (expressed as percentage of dry spent solid) at maximum temperatures assayed.

Fraction	Temperature (°C)							
	180	185	190	195	200	205	210	215
Severity (S ₀)	3.29	3.45	3.60	3.82	4.01	4.28	4.47	4.65
Substrate solubilization	24.2	27.9	30.7	33.8	38.7	38.8	41.1	40.5
Glucan	34.0	32.0	30.0	28.0	27.7	34.4	34.6	34.8
Xylan	12.6	8.5	6.0	4.2	3.3	2.5	1.8	1.7
Arabinosyl substituents	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Galactosyl substituents	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Manosyl substituents	1.5	1.7	1.4	1.2	1.0	1.0	0.6	0.6
Acetyl groups	3.4	3.1	2.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Galacturonic acid	2.7	2.1	1.8	1.5	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.8
Klason lignin	34.1	389.4	44.0	49.0	52.0	54.0	55.1	55.3
Others (by difference)	10.8	12.4	13.3	15.8	14.8	7.0	7.0	6.8

Table 2 shows the effects provoked by the aqueous processing on the composition of the liquors. The hydrothermal treatments under suitable conditions promote reactions in the media that cause the solubilization of hemicelluloses and other fractions generating both non volatile (NVC) and volatile compounds (VC) (Martínez et al., 2009).

The substrate conversion into NVC increased steadily until 200 °C reaching a 27.7% of the initial material (o.d. weight); in the range 200–215 °C the percentage of substrate conversion into NVC decreased slightly (20.9% at 215 °C). These data are in accordance with the non-volatile content (quantified by oven-drying liquors) that reached a maximum at 200 °C (0.0330 g NVC/g liquor) and then, this value decreased until 0.0248 g NVC/g liquor at 215 °C. Similar results have been obtained by Martínez et al. (2009) for processing sugar beet pulp by autohydrolysis. These authors proposed as a possible explanation for this behavior that at lower temperatures (for vine shoots below 200 °C) the major contribution to NVC correspond to the solubilization of the hemicelluloses, extractives and other fractions, whereas the decomposition reactions were predominant at temperature higher (in case of vine shoots processing above 200 °C).

With respect to the substrate conversion into VC, this percentage increased continuously with the temperature until the harsher temperature assayed (19.7%); this increase is in accordance with the generation of volatile compounds that reached a total of 7.72 g/L (acetic acid, HMF, furfural) at

215 °C (see Table 3). The joint contribution of the degradation products was comparatively lower (2.34 g/L at 200 °C) at the temperature leading to the maximum concentration of xylooligosaccharide (12.2 g/L at 200 °C). These data are in agreement with the results published by Moniz et al. (2013) which observed that the optimum temperature for production of the maximum concentration of XOS from corn straw coincided with the temperature in which the concentration of degradation products was relatively low.

Table 2. Effects caused by aqueous processing on the liquors composition.

	Temperature (°C)							
	180	185	190	195	200	205	210	215
Substrate conversion into NVC (% o.d. weight)	17.4	18.6	22.1	24.80	27.7	26.3	23.0	20.9
Substrate conversion into VC (% o.d. weight)	6.8	9.3	8.6	9.0	11.0	12.5	18.2	19.7
ONVC (g/g of NVC)	0.20	0.16	0.15	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.31	0.45
NVC (g NVC/g of liquor)	0.0210	0.0224	0.0266	0.0298	0.0330	0.0313	0.0273	0.0248
Glucan conversion into Glc (%)	0.9	0.9	1.1	0.7	0.8	1.0	1.5	2.6
Xylan conversion into Xyl (%)	0.4	0.5	0.6	1.7	1.9	4.2	6.8	7.0
Arabinosyl substituents conversion into Ara (%)	25.0	26.3	31.4	19.0	21.2	18.3	11.2	10.4
Galactosyl substituents conversion into Ga (%)	6.6	6.7	7.9	6.2	7.0	7.4	9.5	9.2
Manosyl substituents conversion into Man (%)	5.2	4.6	5.5	5.1	5.7	7.6	11.7	17.7
Acetyl groups conversion into acetic acid (%)	12.7	14.2	16.9	34.8	38.8	57.5	75.2	105.8
Galacturonyl substituents conversion into Galacturonic acid (%)	12.2	12.2	14.5	13.1	14.6	13.9	7.8	5.8
Glucan conversion into GOS (%)	15.7	15.8	18.9	19.6	21.8	20.5	14.1	9.0
Xylan conversion into XOS (%)	29.0	39.4	46.9	74.5	83.1	79.0	39.2	18.7
Arabinosyl groups conversion into AOS (%)	37.8	40.1	47.7	38.5	42.9	19.7	16.8	19.7
Galactosyl groups conversion into GaOS (%)	19.6	18.9	22.6	29.8	33.2	20.0	6.4	0.0
Manosyl groups conversion into MaOS (%)	25.6	26.0	30.9	56.0	62.5	50.3	55.8	77.7
Acetyl groups conversion into Ac (%)	24.3	25.9	30.9	18.5	20.6	17.8	15.5	15.9
Galacturonic acid present in soluble components (% of the initial amount)	24.5	30.6	36.5	60.6	66.9	63.8	38.9	31.8

Table 3. Degradation compounds generated in liquid phase (expressed as g compound/L liquor) along aqueous processing at maximum temperatures assayed.

Compound	Temperature (°C)							
	180	185	190	195	200	205	210	215
Acetic acid	0.66	0.73	1.06	1.50	1.99	2.94	3.84	5.41
HMF	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.08	0.15	0.30	0.50
Furfural	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.14	0.27	0.52	1.19	1.81

Fig. 2(A) shows the composition of oligomers in liquors as a function of temperature. The major compounds present in the reaction media were glucooligosaccharides (GOS) and xylooligosaccharides (XOS). The maximum concentration of GOS was 8.64 g/L at 200 °C that corresponds with a conversion of glucan into GOS of 21.8%. XOS were the most abundant of the autohydrolysis products increasing with the temperature until reach a maximum of 12.2 g/L at 200 °C revealing a conversion of the xylan into XOS of 83.1%; however, from 200 °C to 215 °C this concentration decreased until 2.7 g/L. The arabinosyl groups linked to oligomers showed a high susceptibility to the hydrothermal processing. At 190 °C the 47.7% of the arabinose moieties remained linked to oligomers. The concentration of ArOS remained constant until 200 °C (0.73 g/L), then decreased until 0.33 g/L at 205 °C and finally remained without variation. Galactooligosaccharides (GaOS) showed a similar profile to ArOS reaching the maximum concentration at the same temperature (200 °C) (33.2% of conversion galactosyl groups into GaOS). Mannooligosaccharides (MaOS) varied in the range 0.51–1.51 g/L. The behavior of acetyl groups linked to oligomers was analogous to GaOS reaching a maximum of 3.3 g/L at 200 °C corresponding to a conversion of 20.6% of acetyl groups in raw material, when the higher temperature was achieved a decrease in their concentration occurred.

Fig. 2(B) shows the concentration of monomers (glucose, xylose, arabinose, galactose and mannose) and galacturonic acid in the liquors obtained by the autohydrolysis treatments. The concentration of glucose scarcely varied in the range 180–195 °C with a value between 0.37–0.25 g/L coinciding with the maximum generation of GOS; this amount increased until the maximum temperature as consequence of decrease of GOS. The concentration of xylose first increased slowly (until maximum concentration of XOS) and then increased faster as consequence of decrease of XOS at 215 °C. Arabinose concentration varied in the range 0.44–0.18 g/L at the temperature interval 180–215 °C. Concentrations of galactose and mannose remained almost constant until 200 °C and then increased until they reach similar concentrations at 215 °C (0.34 g/L). Galacturonic acid reached a maximum concentration at 200 °C (0.72 g/L) and then decreased until 0.29 g/L at 215 °C.

Fig. 2. Composition of liquors on oligomers and pH as a function of temperature (A). Composition of liquors on monosaccharides as a function of temperature (B).

Finally, there is a fraction called other non volatile compounds (ONVC) or “impurities” that is calculated as the difference between non volatile compounds (NVC) and the joint contribution of saccharides (monosaccharides and oligomers) and correspond to undesired compounds that are present in liquors. Table 2 lists the ONVC at each temperature assayed. It is remarkable that the amount of ONVC varied from 0.20 (g/g of NVC) at lower severity ($S_0 = 3.29$) to 0.08 (g/g of NVC) at intermediate severity ($S_0 = 4.01$) and then this value increased until 0.45 (g/g of NVC) at the harsher severity assayed ($S_0 = 4.65$).

3.2.2. Effects of operational conditions on the composition of spent solids

The major components of the spent solids are the glucan and the Klason lignin. Table 1 shows the data concerning to the chemical composition of the spent solids. For the content of glucan two behaviors were observed; in the range 180–200 °C ($S_0 = 3.29$ and 4.01, respectively) the percentage of glucan decreased from 34 to 27.1% which involves that a 77.6 and 51% of glucan

contained in the raw material was retained in solid phase after processing to 180 and 200 °C, respectively; at 205 °C ($S_0 = 4.28$) the content of glucan increased with respect to 200 °C until 34.4%; this percentage remained almost constant at the harsher severity assayed ($S_0 = 4.65$) revealing that about a 62.4% of the glucan contained in the feedstock was retained in solid fraction. These results are higher than those reported by Vargas et al. (2015) which achieved just 51.2% of glucan recovery for barley straw. In contrast, Gullón et al. (2010) have reported a recovery of 90% for glucan using rye straw.

The content of Klason lignin varied in a wide range, from 34.1% at 180 °C to 55.3% at 215 °C. The spent solids at harsher severity were made up mostly of glucan and lignin; so, at $S_0 = 4.65$ corresponding to 215 °C the joint contribution of glucan and lignin was 90.15%. These results are in agreement with the reported by other authors who had informed that these fractions show less susceptibility to aqueous treatments (Martínez et al., 2010b; Gullón et al., 2010). Yáñez et al. (2009) have obtained spent solids at highest temperatures exclusively composed of glucan and lignin using *Acacia dealbata* wood.

Contrary to the case of the glucan and lignin, the percentage of hemicellulosic fraction in the solid phase decreased continuously with the severity of treatments (see Table 1). The total amount of hemicellulosic fraction (xylan, arabinosyl substituents, galactosyl substituents, manosyl substituents, galacturonyl substituents, acetyl groups) varied from 21.1% at 180 °C to 3.08% at 215 °C revealing the selectivity of the hydrothermal treatments to remove these fraction from vine shoots. At the highest severity ($S_0 = 4.65$) the residual xylan in spent solid was 8% with respect to the xylan contained in raw material, while arabinosyl, galactosyl and galacturonyl substituents were solubilized completely, and the recovery of manosyl substituents and acetyl groups was 23.2% and 10.8%, respectively. The results obtained in this work are in the line with the reported by Moniz et al. (2013): these authors worked with corn straw which showed a very significant solubilization of xylan at the severest conditions assayed (240 °C) with a 2.7% of residual xylan into treated solid.

Taking into account the above results, and as it has been described for other agroindustrial feedstocks, the hemicellulosic components from the vine shoots were solubilized selectively by the hydrothermal treatments, providing a high recovery of both cellulose and lignin in solid fraction (Garrote et al., 2007a). It is expected that the spent solids from these pretreatments present an enhanced susceptibility toward other processes for the obtaining of variety of interesting products allowing an integrated revalorization of this feedstock.

3.3. Structural characterization of fractions from autohydrolysis reaction

3.3.1. Molecular weight distribution of the autohydrolysis liquors

Because the potential applications of oligosaccharides are directly related with their molar weight distribution, additional characterization was carried out. Moreover, the determination of molecular weight distribution of oligosaccharides contained into reaction liquors allows us to establish an interrelationship between the treatment severity and the molecular weight distribution. The molecular weight distribution of the hemicelluloses contained in the autohydrolysis liquors obtained at different temperatures was analyzed by HPSEC in combination with RI-detection, as it is shown in the Fig. 3(A). Hemicelluloses fractions with different molecular weight were obtained depending on the severity of the autohydrolysis treatment. The weight average (Mw), the number average (Mn) and the polydispersity degree (Mw/Mn) of each fraction are indicated in Table 4.

Fig. 3. GPC elution patterns determined for non purified autohydrolysis liquors obtained at different temperatures (A). Relative proportions of fractions with high, medium and low molecular weight hemicelluloses in non purified liquors obtained at different temperatures (B).

The hemicelluloses contained in the liquors can be classified depending of their molecular weight as low molecular weight hemicelluloses (~200 Da), medium molecular weight hemicelluloses (~10.000 Da) and high molecular weight (~100.000 Da) (Tunc and Van Heiningen, 2011). The percentage of each fraction in the liquors is calculated by the percentage of the area, assuming that in the HPSEC chromatograms the areas underneath the RI graphs were proportional to the

eluted saccharides. Apart from these fractions, there is a fraction with molecular weight lower than 180 Da that has been taken into account in the total area for calculating the percentage of each fraction of hemicelluloses.

As it is illustrated in the Fig. 3(B), when autohydrolysis treatments with low severity were carried out there was a small fraction of high molecular weight hemicelluloses that disappeared with the increase of the severity. The medium molecular weight hemicellulosic fraction was present in all autohydrolysis liquors; however its abundance decreased with the increase of the severity of the treatment. As the autohydrolysis conditions become harsher the degradation of the hemicelluloses in the reaction media increases, which produces an increased in the low molecular weight fraction, being the predominant hemicellulosic fraction in the liquors obtained at high autohydrolysis temperature. It was also observed that with the increase of the severity of the treatment the polydispersity of the whole hemicellulosic fraction decreases from Mw/Mn of 55.72 at 180 °C to 6.02 at 215 °C, which suggests that the molecular weight distribution is getting narrower (Sun et al., 2010).

The trend observed with the hemicellulosic fractions of different molecular weights in the autohydrolysis liquors has been previously reported in the application of this treatment to rice husks or to *Eucalyptus globulus* (Garrote et al., 2007b).

Table 4. The percentage, average molecular weight (Mw), number average (Mn) and polydispersity index (Mw/Mn) of the different fractions of hemicelluloses present in the autohydrolysis liquors at the assayed temperatures.

T (°C)	High molecular weight fraction				Medium molecular weight fraction				Low molecular weight fraction			
	%	Mw (Da)	Mn	Mw/Mn	%	Mw (Da)	Mn	Mw/Mn	%	Mw (Da)	Mn	Mw/Mn
180	6.8	145,770	110,191	1.32	44.5	8318	3613	2.49	42.8	455	124	1.59
185	5.9	85,483	124,143	1.35	42.83	6142	3262	1.88	42.5	437	107	1.88
190	-	-	-	-	50.57	10390	3153	3.29	44.61	416	124	3.34
195	-	-	-	-	41.32	6440	3150	2.04	54.27	487	130	3.74
200	-	-	-	-	41.32	4449	2698	1.64	54.37	485	169	2.86
205	-	-	-	-	27.64	3944	2958	1.34	68.48	564	178	3.16
210	-	-	-	-	17.28	4330	3556	1.21	78.11	627	199	3.15
215	-	-	-	-	20.06	4026	3239	1.24	75.01	550	170	3.22

3.3.2. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTGA)

Thermal analysis (thermogravimetric (TG) and first derivative (DTG) curves) of lyophilized autohydrolysis liquors are presented in Figs. 4 and 5(A and B). Depending on the severity of autohydrolysis treatment, some differences on thermal decomposition curves were observed. All

the autohydrolysis liquors presented a 31–35% of the char residue obtained at 600 °C and a small initial weight loss (3–4%) below 100 °C, which was assigned to the gradual evaporation of moisture. The main decomposition stage related to the hemicelluloses degradation occurs in the temperature range between 100 and 350 °C, it has been previously reported that the degradation of hemicelluloses takes place between 200 and 320 °C (Egüés et al., 2013). Fig. 4 shows that with the increase of the severity of the treatment the thermogravimetric curves shift to lower temperatures. In the main decomposition stage which is represented in Fig. 4, three degradation steps take place, as it is revealed in the Fig. 5(A and B). The different degradation steps correspond to the different hemicelluloses fractions in each sample observed previously by HPSEC. It was observed that the maximum degradation temperature (T^a_{max}) was influenced by the severity of the treatment, decreasing it with the increase of the severity (Table 5). When the liquor is mainly composed by high molecular weight fractions as in the case of the autohydrolysis performed at 180 °C, the maximum weight loss rate happened at 272 °C, while the liquor composed mainly by low molecular weight fractions, performed at 215 °C, showed T^a_{max} at 186 °C. This tendency can be explained by the assumption that the thermostability of the hemicelluloses increases as the molecular weight increases (Sun et al., 2002).

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric analysis spectra of autohydrolysis liquors obtained at different temperatures.

3.3.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectra of the lyophilized autohydrolysis liquors have been obtained at different temperatures. These spectra show the typical transmittance bands expected for hemicellulosic polymers and the peak assignment was carried taking into account what has been reported in literature (Jiang et al., 2014). The signal observed at 1035 cm^{-1} was assigned to the maximum specific signal of hemicelluloses and is due to the stretching and bending vibrations of C-O, C-C, C-OH and the glycosidic C-O-C, indicating a dominant xylan oligosaccharides, which was supported by the results obtained in analysis of the composition of the liquors. The small band observed at 896 cm^{-1} could correspond to C_1 group frequency or ring frequency, suggesting the

presence of β -glycosidic linkages between xylopiranoses units in the main xylan chain. The signal observed at 1149 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of arabinosyl side chains and the band at 1075 cm^{-1} indicated the glycosidic bond vibrations of arabinoxylans (Egüés et al., 2010). The presence of acetic acid and galacturonic acid, apart from the results obtained in the analysis of the composition of the liquors, was confirmed by the presence of a band at 1729 cm^{-1} and 1595 cm^{-1} respectively. A small band observed at 1510 cm^{-1} could correspond to the C=C stretching of the aromatic ring, which can reveal that small amount of lignin could remain associated to the oligosaccharides.

Fig. 5. Derivative DTG curves of autohydrolysis liquors obtained at 180, 185, 190 and 195 °C (A). Derivative DTG curves of autohydrolysis liquors obtained at 200, 205, 210 and 215 °C (B).

Table 5. The maximum weight loss temperature and the char residue at 600 °C of the lyophilized liquors.

Pretreatment (°C)	Tmax (°C)	Solid residue (%)
180	272.4	31.6
185	275.2	31.5
190	271.3	32.0
195	216.0	31.0
200	203.0	32.4
205	201.2	35.0
210	190.2	34.4
215	186.2	34.9

Apart from the autohydrolysis liquors, the raw material and the solid phases obtained after the autohydrolysis pretreatments were analyzed by FTIR. Compared with the FTIR spectra obtained

from the autohydrolysis liquors, these ones presented differences and some additional peaks that indicate the presence of cellulose and lignin in the solid phases, which is supported by the results obtained in the chemical analysis. With the increase of the severity of the autohydrolysis pretreatment the intensity of the band observed at 1740 cm^{-1} , which corresponded to the C=O stretching vibration due to the carbonyl bonds of the acetyl groups in xylan (Michell and Higgins, 1999) decreased. This tendency was also observed in the intensity of the signal that appears at 1265 cm^{-1} , which is associated with the cleavage and/or alteration of acetyl groups (Moniz et al., 2013). This was also supported by the increase of acetic acid in the autohydrolysis liquors with the severity of the treatment, which is observed in the decrease of the pH shown in the Fig. 2(A). The signal observed at 1624 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of lignin, as it is associated with the increase of lignin condensation reactions (Kaparaju and Felby, 2010). It was also observed that the intensity of the signal observed at 1520 cm^{-1} , which is associated with the aromatic skeletal vibration in lignin (Egüés et al., 2010) increases with the severity of the pretreatment. The band observed at 1330 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C-H vibration in cellulose (Meor Hussin et al., 2013) indicating its presence in the solid phases.

4. Conclusions

Vine shoots were subjected to autohydrolysis concluding that the extent hemicelluloses depolymerization depended on the severity of the hydrothermal processing. The maximum xylan conversion into XOS was 83.1% at $S_0 = 4.01$ and the concentration of XOS was 12.2 g/L with a content of ONVC of 0.08 (g/g of NVC). The spent solid from this treatment was composed mostly of cellulose and lignin that can be separated in further processes. Therefore, the hydrothermal processing of vine shoots proposed in this work is a suitable pretreatment as a first stage of a biorefinery scope allowing an integrated valorization of vine shoots.

Acknowledgements

Izaskun Dávila would like to thank the Agriculture, Fishing and Food Department of the Basque Government (scholarship of young researchers training). Oihana Gordobil would like to thank the University of the Basque Country for the doctoral grant (Reference PIF 13/050) and Patricia Gullón would like to thank the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness for her postdoctoral grant (Reference FPDI-2013-18748).

References

Bustos, G., Moldes, A.B., Cruz, J.M., Domínguez, J.M., 2004. Production of fermentable media from vine-trimming wastes and bioconversion into lactic acid by *Lactobacillus pentosus*. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 84, 2105–2112.

- Carvalho, F., Esteves, M.P., Parajó, J.C., Pereira, H., Girio, F.M., 2004. Production of oligosaccharides by autohydrolysis of brewery's spent grain. *Bioresour. Technol.* 91, 93–100.
- Chemin, M., Wirotius, A.L., Ham-Pichavant, F., Chollet, G., Da Silva, D., Petit-Conil, M., Cramail, H., Grelier, S., 2015. Well-defined oligosaccharides by mild acidic hydrolysis of hemicelluloses. *Eur. Polym. J.* 66, 190–197.
- Delgado-Torre, M.P., Ferreiro-Vera, C., Priego-Capote, F., Pérez-Juan, P.M., Luque De Castro, M.D., 2012. Comparison of accelerated methods for the extraction of phenolic compounds from different vine-shoot cultivars. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 60, 3051–3060.
- Deutschmann, R., Dekker, R.F.H., 2012. From a plant biomass to bio-based chemicals: latest developments in xylan research. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 30, 1627–1640.
- Egüés, I., González Alriols, M., Herseczki, Z., Marton, G., Labidi, J., 2010. Hemicelluloses obtaining from rapeseed cake residue generated in the biodiesel production process. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 16, 293–298.
- Egüés, I., Eceiza, A., Labidi, J., 2013. Effect of different hemicelluloses characteristics on film forming properties. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 47, 331–338.
- Garrote, G., Falqué, E., Domínguez, H., Parajó, J.C., 2007a. Autohydrolysis of agricultural residues: study of reaction byproducts. *Bioresour. Technol.* 98, 1951–1957.
- Garrote, G., Kabel, M.A., Schols, H.A., Falqué, E., Domínguez, H., Parajó, J.C., 2007b. Effects of Eucalyptus globulus wood autohydrolysis conditions on the reaction products. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 55, 9006–9013.
- Gullón, P., Pereiro, G., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2009. Aqueous pretreatment of agricultural wastes: characterization of soluble reaction products. *Bioresour. Technol.* 100, 5840–5845.
- Gullón, B., Yañez, R., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2010. Production of oligosaccharides and sugars from rye straw: a kinetic approach. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101, 6676–6684.
- Jiang, H., Chen, Q., Ge, J., Zhang, Y., 2014. Efficient extraction and characterization of polymeric hemicelluloses from hybrid poplar. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 101, 1005–1012.
- Jiménez, L., Angulo, V., García, G., Rodríguez, A., 2004. Cellulosic pulp from vine shoots. *Afinidad* 61, 194–203.
- Jiménez, L., Pérez, A., de la Torre, M.J., Moral, A., Serrano, L., 2007. Characterization of vine shoots, cotton stalks, *Leucaena leucocephala* and *Chamaecytisus proliferus*, and of their ethyleneglycol pulps. *Bioresour. Technol.* 98, 3487–3490.

- Kaparaju, P., Felby, C., 2010. Characterization of lignin during oxidative and hydrothermal pre-treatment processes of wheat straw and corn stover. *Bioresour. Technol.* 101, 3175–3181.
- Marculescu, C., Ciuta, S., 2013. Wine industry waste thermal processing for derived fuel properties improvement. *Renewable Energy* 57, 645–652.
- Martínez, M., Gullón, B., Schols, H.A., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2009. Assessment of the production of oligomeric compounds from sugar beet pulp. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 48, 4681–4687.
- Martínez, M., Gullón, B., Yáñez, R., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2010a. Kinetic assessment on the autohydrolysis of pectin-rich by-products. *Chem. Eng. J.* 162, 480–486.
- Martínez, M., Yáñez, R., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2010b. Chemical production of pectic oligosaccharides from orange peel wastes. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 49, 8470–8476.
- Max, B., Salgado, J.M., Cortés, S., Domínguez, J.M., 2010. Extraction of phenolic acids by alkaline hydrolysis from the solid residues obtained after prehydrolysis of trimming vine shoots. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 58, 1909–1917.
- Meor Hussin, A.S., Collins, S.R.A., Merali, Z., Parker, M.L., Ellinston, A., Wellner, N., Waldron, K.W., 2013. Characterisation of lignocellulosic sugars from municipal solid waste residue. *Biomass Bioenergy* 51, 17–25.
- Michell, A.J., Higgins, H.G., 1999. The absence of free hydroxyl groups in cellulose. *Cellulose* 6, 89–91.
- Moldes, A.B., Bustos, G., Torrado, A., Domínguez, J.M., 2007. Comparison between different hydrolysis processes of vine-trimming waste to obtain hemicellulosic sugars for further lactic acid conversion. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 143, 244–256.
- Moniz, P., Pereira, H., Quilhó, T., Carvalheiro, F., 2013. Characterisation and hydrothermal processing of corn straw towards the selective fractionation of hemicelluloses. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 50, 145–153.
- Nabais, J.M.V., Laginhas, C., Carrott, P.J.M., Carrott, M.M.L.R., 2010. Thermal conversion of a novel biomass agricultural residue (vine shoots) into activated carbon using activation with CO₂. *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 87, 8–13.
- Rivas, B., Torrado, A., Rivas, S., Moldes, A.B., Domínguez, J.M., 2007. Simultaneous lactic acid and xylitol production from vine trimming wastes. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 87, 1603–1612.
- Rivas, S., Gullón, B., Gullón, P., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2012. Manufacture and properties of bifidogenic saccharides derived from wood mannan. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 60, 4296–4305.

- Sánchez-Gómez, R., Zalacain, A., Alonso, G.L., Salinas, M.R., 2014. Vine-shoot waste aqueous extracts for re-use in agriculture obtained by different extraction techniques: phenolic, volatile and mineral compounds. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 62, 10861–10872.
- Sun, X.F., Sun, R.C., Lu, Q., Xu, F., Lin, L., 2002. Fractional isolation and physicochemical characterization of hemicelluloses by a two-stage treatment from *Haloxylon ammodendron* and *Elaeagnus angustifolia*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 50, 6400–6407.
- Sun, X.F., Fowler, P., Rajaratnam, M., Zhang, G., 2010. Extraction and characterization of hemicelluloses from maize stem. *Phytochem. Anal.* 21, 406–415.
- Teixeira, A., Baenas, N., Dominguez-Perles, R., Barros, A., Rosa, E., Moreno, D.A., Garcia-Viguera, C., 2014. Natural bioactive compounds from winery byproducts as health promoters: a review. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 15, 15638–15678.
- Tunc, M.S., Van Heiningen, A.R.P., 2011. Characterization and molecular weight distribution of carbohydrates isolated from the autohydrolysis extract of mixed southern hardwoods. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 83, 8–13.
- Vargas, F., Domínguez, E., Vila, C., Rodríguez, A., Garrote, G., 2015. Agricultural residue valorization using a hydrothermal process for second generation bioethanol and oligosaccharides production. *Bioresour. Technol.* 191, 263–270.
- Vegas, R., Alonso, J.L., Domínguez, H., Parajó, J.C., 2005. Manufacture and refining of oligosaccharides from industrial solid wastes. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 44, 614–620.
- Yáñez, R., Romaní, A., Garrote, G., Alonso, J.L., Parajó, J.C., 2009. Processing of *Acacia dealbata* in aqueous media: first step of a wood biorefinery. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 48, 6618–6626.